

STRENGTHENING STUDENTS' THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE AND FORMING PRACTICAL COMPETENCES THROUGH EXPERIMENTATION

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Abstract. *Improving the effectiveness of teaching physics is one of the most pressing issues in the modern education system. In new-generation curricula, a significant role is given to the approach of assessing the mastery of physical knowledge based on a system of achievement levels, where progression to each subsequent level is ensured only through thorough mastery of the previous one [1]. A teaching methodology based on the implementation of a system–activity approach through school physics experiments is proposed. Within this approach, not only students' conceptual knowledge but also their active participation in acquiring new knowledge is considered a key criterion [2]. Using the experiment of determining the electrical capacitance of capacitors with the help of an ammeter and a voltmeter as an example, the article highlights the possibilities of strengthening students' theoretical knowledge and developing their practical competencies through experimental instruction [3].*

Keywords: *practical competence, cognition, laboratory work, experiment, observation, investigation, physical experiment, capacitor, capacitance.*

Introduction

An experiment is a means of transforming theoretical knowledge into practical experience and plays an important role in developing students' independent thinking, problem-solving abilities, and research competencies [4]. In order to organize experiments effectively in the educational process, the following stages are implemented: problem formulation, hypothesis development, conducting measurements, processing results, and drawing conclusions.

For students to acquire an adequate level of knowledge of the fundamental laws and principles related to each topic in physics, the teacher should not limit instruction to oral explanation of the learning material but should also conduct experiments corresponding to the topic. This approach facilitates visualization of physical phenomena and contributes to the development of cognitive activity and thinking skills [1]. In some topics, conducting experiments requires not only a single instrument but also several devices and components. Therefore, laboratory work in physics is directly dependent on the material and technical resources of the educational laboratory [2]. The use of modern equipment makes it possible to obtain more accurate results and to organize the teaching–learning process more effectively.

Laboratory sessions foster students' abilities to work both individually and collaboratively, developing skills and habits of planning and systematic work. In addition, they enable teachers to continuously monitor students' knowledge, skills, and competencies, while providing students with opportunities for self-assessment and self-control [5]. The implementation of an integrated approach in the educational process plays a significant role, particularly in developing students' practical competencies through physics-based experiments. As an illustrative example, a laboratory session focused on determining the capacitance of capacitors is presented below [3].

Determination of the electrical capacitance of capacitors using an ammeter and a voltmeter.

Required equipment and materials:

1. A capacitor whose capacitance is to be determined.
2. A capacitor with a known capacitance.
3. A voltmeter with high internal resistance.
4. An ammeter.
5. A conductor with a known active resistance.
6. Connecting wires.

Figure 1

Figure 2

To determine the capacitance of a capacitor using this method, one of the electrical circuit diagrams shown in Figures 1, 2, or 3 is assembled. In these circuits, C_x denotes the capacitor (or capacitor bank) whose capacitance is to be determined, A is an ammeter, V_1 and V_2 are voltmeters, R represents a known active resistance, C indicates a capacitor with known capacitance, and E is the power supply.

If the first circuit is used, then according to Ohm's law, the capacitive reactance of the capacitor is

$$R_c = \frac{U}{I} \quad (1)$$

Since $R_c = \frac{1}{\omega C_x}$ (2) on the basis of equations (1) and (2), the following relationship is obtained:

$$\frac{U}{I} = \frac{1}{\omega C_x}$$

Taking into account that $C_x = \frac{I}{U\omega}$, $\omega = 2\pi\nu$, the capacitance can be calculated as

$$C_x = \frac{I}{2\pi\nu U} \quad (3)$$

Thus, equation (3) is obtained, where U and I denote the readings of the voltmeter and the ammeter, respectively. If the second circuit is used, considering that in a series connection the same current flows through each conductor, the potential drop across the resistance R is

$U_1 = IR$, and the potential drop across the capacitor with capacitance C_x whose capacitive

reactance is $R_{C_x} = \frac{1}{2\pi\nu C_x}$ is $U_2 = IR_{C_x}$.

Since

$$I = \frac{U_1}{R} \text{ and } I = \frac{U_2}{R_{C_x}},$$

we obtain

$$\frac{U_1}{R} = \frac{U_2}{R_{C_x}} = 2\pi\nu C_x U_2.$$

From this relation, the capacitance is determined as

$$C_x = \frac{U_1}{2\pi\nu R U_2} \quad (4)$$

If the third circuit is used, a capacitor **C** with known capacitance and resistance is connected in series with a capacitor C_x of unknown capacitance and resistance R_x . Under these conditions, $U_1 = IR_C$, $U_2 = IR_{C_x}$. From these expressions, the following relation is obtained:

$$\frac{U_1}{R_C} = \frac{U_2}{R_{C_x}}. \text{ Substituting the expressions for } R_C \text{ and } R_{C_x}, \text{ we obtain:}$$

$$2\pi\nu C U_1 = 2\pi\nu C_x U_2. \text{ From this formula, the unknown capacitance } C_x \text{ is determined.}$$

In equations (4) and (5), U_1 and U_2 denote the readings of voltmeters V_1 and V_2 , respectively.

Figure 3

To determine the capacitance of the capacitor, the circuit diagrams are used based on Ohm's law and the formulas of capacitive reactance [1]. By selecting one of the circuits shown in Figures 1–3, the experimental procedure is carried out step by step. Based on the measurement results, the capacitance is calculated using formulas (3), (4), and (5). During the experiment, students apply their theoretical knowledge in practice, identify errors, compare the results, and perform analysis. This process fosters the development of their analytical thinking and scientific research skills [7].

Experimental Procedure

1. One of the electrical circuits shown in Figures 1, 2, or 3 is assembled.
2. By gradually varying the voltage, the corresponding readings of the voltmeter **V** and the ammeter **A**, or the readings of voltmeters V_1 and V_2 , are recorded for each voltage value.
3. Based on these measurements, the capacitance of the capacitor is calculated using one of the formulas (3), (4), or (5).
4. For the capacitor with unknown capacitance, the average value, as well as the absolute and relative errors, are calculated on the basis of the obtained results.

5. When a capacitor bank composed of capacitors with known capacitance is used as the unknown capacitance, the experiment is also carried out in accordance with steps 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

6. If the shape and dimensions of the capacitor whose capacitance has been determined are known, the capacitance is additionally calculated using the appropriate formulas for determining the capacitance of capacitors according to their geometric shape, and the experimental results are recorded in the following table. Thus, during the performance of this laboratory work, students independently apply and reinforce the theoretical knowledge they have acquired in practice. Such experiment-based instruction effectively develops students' analytical thinking, scientific research, and independent decision-making skills.

No	ν (Hz)	U (V)	I (A)	C_x (μF)	$\langle C_x \rangle$ (μF)	ΔC_x (μF)	$\langle \Delta C_x \rangle$ (μF)	ε %
1	50	9,5	101	33,85	33,3	0,55	0,37	1,1
2		6,5	68	33,31		0,01		
3		3,5	36	32,75		0,55		

Review Questions

1. What is meant by the electrical capacitance of a capacitor? What units is it measured in?
2. When capacitors are connected in series, which quantity remains the same for all of them, and how is the equivalent capacitance calculated?
3. When capacitors are connected in parallel, which quantity is common for all capacitors, and which formula is used to determine the total capacitance?
4. Why must the polarity be observed when an electrolytic capacitor is connected to an electric circuit?
5. How does changing the source voltage influence the charging and discharging time of a capacitor? What effect does a change in the resistance of the resistor have?

Conclusion

The conducted analysis shows that experiment-based teaching enriches the content of physics lessons, ensures a strong connection between theory and practice, and involves students in the learning process as active participants. This, in turn, contributes to the formation of stable subject-related motivation among students and prepares them to independently solve more complex problems at subsequent stages [5, 6]. Therefore, the widespread implementation of this methodological approach in physics lessons of general education schools serves as an important factor in achieving high educational outcomes.

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